

When will the Kingdom of Heaven on Earth be Established?

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Mark 8:1-10

Mark 8:1 In those days, when there was again a large crowd and they had nothing to eat, Jesus called His disciples and said to them, ² “I feel compassion for the people because they have remained with Me now three days and have nothing to eat. ³ “If I send them away hungry to their homes, they will faint on the way; and some of them have come from a great distance.” ⁴ And His disciples answered Him, “Where will anyone be able to *find enough* bread here in *this* desolate place to satisfy these people?” ⁵ And He was asking them, “How many loaves do you have?” And they said, “Seven.” ⁶ And He directed the ¹people to ²sit down on the ground; and taking the seven loaves, He gave thanks and broke them, and started giving them to His disciples to serve to them, and they served them to the people. ⁷ They also had a few small fish; and after He had blessed them, He ordered these to be ¹served as well. ⁸ And they ate and were satisfied; and they picked up seven large baskets full of what was left over of the broken pieces. ⁹ About four thousand were *there*; and He sent them away. ¹⁰ And immediately He entered the boat with His disciples and came to the district of Dalmanutha.

At the literary level, this feeding of 4,000 people reads like a simple story. However, there was a large number of people who wanted to hear Jesus speak. Jesus wanted to ensure that they were not hungry, so he feeds them. The story is simple. However, moving from the literary reading to the allegorical interpretation of the story produces many lessons. The food is symbolic of spiritual lessons. Thus, Jesus was teaching the people that they needed spiritual food as much as dietary food.

For example, the number seven is the key to the meaning of this feeding. The Kingdom of Heaven is not complete until the Gentiles were included. Seven is the symbol of completion. Jesus' work in saving humankind is not complete until all the people of the world are included. The divine intervention of the LORD is indicated to us by having a three-day event. Three is symbolic of divinity and divine intervention. The seven loaves and seven baskets of left-overs symbolize the inclusion of all people, Hebrew and Gentiles.

It is sad that there were people in the church throughout its history and even today who do not believe that every person in the world can belong to Christ. Even Martin

Luther, the great reformer, said that Jesus was not Jewish. Later in his life, he retracted that claim. Unfortunately, quite a bit of damage occurred during the last five hundred years because of his statement.

The Kingdom of Heaven on Earth is meant to be inclusive of all people. When every person in the world is a part of the Kingdom, then Jesus' work is complete. Perhaps this is the event that will trigger the Isaiah prophecy of a new heaven and new Earth. Just having people loving each other instead of killing and hating each other would be enough to make the transition. Imagine a world without war, crime, or hate. Can you do that? Well, you have just imagined what the Kingdom of Heaven is all about.

An attribute of Heaven is that only love exists. Therefore, before a person can enter Heaven, the soul must be cleansed. All negative emotions about any other person must be purged. The Zohar says that a person will go to Avadon for a period to be purified for Heaven. Even the righteous will go through this exercise. The soul cannot enter Heaven if there is any hatred left. Heaven is a place of pure thoughts and actions. Therefore, all sin must be purged before the soul can enter.

Jesus wanted to expand the purity of Heaven to the Earth. In His time, there was a lot of hatred and oppression. These are not permitted features in Heaven and certainly not in the Kingdom of Heaven. If purity could be brought to the Earth, then the soul would not have to spend any time in Avadon. A post-death purification would not be necessary. Thus, souls could move onto Heaven more quickly. Also, the problems of Earth would fade into dust if everyone learned to love one another.

Jesus shared the spiritual food necessary for the world to become the Kingdom of Heaven on Earth. Read His words in the Bible, and if you live by them, you will bring yourself one giant step closer to Heaven.

May the LORD bless you in your learning and studying of His Word.